

O-RAN Neutral Hosting as a Viable Solution for First Responders Seamless Connectivity

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Abstract—Seamless connectivity is critical for first responders in emergency situations, where communications can be impaired by disrupted infrastructures and network congestion. O-RAN targets unprecedented openness of radio access networks which may be beneficial in critical conditions where the integration among operator networks may compensate scarce availability of resources. In this work we propose an O-RAN-based architectural approach exploiting neutral hosting as a unified access to Radio Access Network (RAN) infrastructures. The proposed approach offers transparent access to first responders and efficiently accommodates resources at RAN and Core level in an area of interest thanks to near-real-time applications (xApps) and non-real-time applications (rApps) hosted by the neutral host.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the modern era, information and communication technologies (ICT) have revolutionized various aspects of human life, including public safety solutions. The integration of ICT tools and systems has significantly transformed the way governments, organizations, and individuals address and manage public safety concerns [1]. The evolution of public safety solutions through ICT has brought about enhanced efficiency, effectiveness, and responsiveness in safeguarding communities, in particular through the exploitation of

- available reliable and fast communication technologies,
- real-time data analytics,
- a proactive and preventive approach achievable for instance through a Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) deployed on critical areas [2].

Particularly focusing on advanced communication systems and data analytics solutions, the proliferation of mobile technologies has also undoubtedly empowered citizens to become active participants in public safety efforts both consciously and unconsciously [3].

Either in the case where the mobile network is used by citizens in emergency situations or in the case where it is used by rescuers following a disaster, it is essential that connectivity is ensured as constantly as possible [4]. From the networking infrastructure point of view, the advent of a natural or a human inducted hazard may cause damage to antenna towers, thus deactivating radio access points and parallelly congesting the ones available, while providing connectivity for first responders is a crucial task. In order to find efficient

and fast solutions for connectivity guarantee in the context of public protection and disaster relief (PPDR [5]), various works have been presented in literature proposing different rapidly deployable networks (RDNs).

The targeted efficiency and rapidity in deploying connectivity solutions to support rescuers calls for new technological approaches. In this work, the exploitation of two technological enablers is investigated for supporting first responders: seamless connectivity which is *neutral hosting* and *O-RAN*.

One major obstacle to provide unified and seamless connectivity to first responders is the heterogeneity of mobile network providers, which public authorities and emergency services management systems have to interact with. Neutral hosting enables a third-party to invest in building the infrastructure for the public mobile access network, that can be made available to mobile network operators (MNOs). From the economical perspective neutral hosting represents a way to lower costs since it offers the possibility for the telecommunications company to be liberated from the burden of constructing the foundational infrastructure of the network, thus reducing the risks associated with deployment. From the technological perspective the neutral host retains network visibility and control and represents a unifying layer for multiple operators able to enhance flexibility [6]. Under the emergency services connectivity perspective this represents a promising opportunity to have a unified interface towards the communication infrastructures to efficiently support emergency connectivity.

While Neutral Hosting simplifies the network infrastructure landscape, O-RAN offers a technological framework to make mobile radio access networks open, flexible, and programmable. O-RAN is an emerging architectural concept that aims to redefine traditional approaches in the existing RAN. O-RAN promotes an open and disaggregated architecture by enabling interoperability, collaboration among various network elements and vendors [7]. O-RAN leverages virtualization and cloud-native principles to enable scalability, efficient resource utilization, and dynamic allocation of network functions. By decoupling hardware and software functionalities, in line with Software Defined Networking paradigm, O-RAN allows for the integration of diverse and innovative solutions, fostering competition and driving technological advancements in the industry. The incorporation of open interfaces and standardized

Fig. 2. Core Network Components Instantiation.

interface to interact with a so-called Non-Real Time (Non-RT) Radio Intelligent Controller (RIC) hosted at the SMO. Since the SMO oversees functions orchestration and is responsible to deploy 5G Core network functions — Access Management Function (AMF), Session Management Function (SMF), Network repository Function (NRF), and User Plane Functions (UPFs) — for the EO. Such functions can be deployed over an edge computing node to offer low latency to first responders. It is worth noticing that computing infrastructure at the edge may be affected by failures due to critical events. In this case the SMO can take alternate orchestration decision and deploy functions over other computation nodes in the O-RAN O-Cloud.

To enforce radio allocation strategies purposely designed for first responders' UEs, the Non-RT RIC interacts via A1 interface with a Near-RT RIC which is responsible to take care of $> 10\text{ms}$ and $< 1\text{s}$ operations (e.g. scheduling and channel monitoring). On top of the Near-RT RIC, an xApp (Emergency Connectivity xApp) is hosted to apply desired allocation strategies able to guarantee upstream (US) and downstream (DS) resources in Orthogonal Frequency Multiple Access (OFDMA) e.g. through Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs) reservation. The Near-RT RIC, in turn interacts with the radio infrastructures via the ORAN E2 interface. As a result, the connected emergency vehicle shown as an example in Fig.1 relies on seamless connectivity with guaranteed resources while moving in the area of interest.

III. FIRST RESPONDERS CONNECTIVITY VIA O-RAN NEUTRAL HOSTING

As described in Section II, interaction between heterogeneous elements is needed to deploy the envisioned Emergency

Connectivity service for first responders. Such interactions are required at both the Core and RAN levels. Figure. 2 shows the sequence diagram of the operations needed to establish Core network functions for the Emergency Service. After the detection of a critical event (which can be automatically injected at the OSS by a Disaster Management System or manually via human operator action) the Emergency Service OSS informs the SMO on the need to deploy an Emergency Service connectivity. At this stage, the OSS can also specify the geographical area where the connectivity is needed and the UEs related information (e.g. International Mobile Subscriber Identities (IMSI)) to be supported for the first responders. The SMO then performs the deployment and configuration of AMF, UPF, SMF, and NRF to realize the EO Core. This operation can be accomplished via orchestration automation tools as shown in [8]. Once Core network functions are deployed the SMO exploits the ORAN O1 Interface to configure the RAN infrastructure elements such as gNodeBs Central Units (CUs) to interact with the EO AMF and to accommodate the slices and users supported by the EO with the help of Slice Service Type (SSD) and Slice Differentiator (SD) definitions. Note that SST and SD can be used to define multiple slices for the EO since first responders might make use of heterogeneous services in terms of latency, bandwidth, and reliability (e.g. extended reality, connected emergency vehicle, etc). Once the EO service is initiated, UEs can be authenticated and traffic can be forwarded between the UEs up to the EO UPF to reach then the data network destination (either available at the edge for low latency service or over the internet).

Once the Core network elements are established, RAN resources must be accommodated. Figure. 3 shows the sequence diagram of the operations needed to support EO at RAN

Fig. 3. O-RAN control.

level. Upon the Emergency Connectivity request issued by the Emergency Service OSS and handled by the Emergency Support rApp, a new policy for radio resource allocation is setup and passed by the Non-RT RIC to the Near-RT RIC via A1 interface. Here, the Emergency Scheduling xApp is in charge of detecting the specific policy for first responders radio connectivity and reserving radio resources according to the desired service requirements. As for the Core network side, also the allocation could take into account the presence of multiple slices for the EO and allocate PRBs accordingly.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

O-RAN neutral hosting emerges as a promising solution to address the seamless connectivity requirements of first responders in emergency situations. In this work we examined the key characteristics, benefits, and challenges associated with O-RAN neutral hosting. By providing an open and flexible framework for deploying and managing radio access networks, O-RAN neutral hosting offers several technical benefits for first responders. The ability to enhance network resilience and redundancy through virtualization and cloud-native principles allows for efficient resource utilization and dynamic allocation of network functions.

Scalability and flexibility of O-RAN neutral hosting enable efficient resource allocation in real-time, accommodating the specific needs of first responders in different emergency scenarios. The prioritization of access and quality of service ensures that critical communications for first responders receive the necessary bandwidth and low latency required for their operations.

As further research and development focus on advancements in O-RAN technology, additional challenges are posed such as integration with optical and satellites transport networks, utilization of artificial intelligence and machine learning for O-RAN optimization, and the exploitation of O-RAN for

enhanced reliability for critical services as first responders connectivity that we plan to explore in future works.

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